

New methods of teaching English in higher education

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13121655>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 12-iyul 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15-iyul 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 29-iyul 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

*foreign language, basic methods, tasks,
teaching a foreign language.*

ABSTRACT

The article discusses different ways of teaching foreign languages in universities. Particular attention was paid to the following methods: direct method, grammatical-translational, audio-visual, audio-lingual and communicative.

There are many ways to learn a foreign language in higher education today. Each of the methods has certain characteristics, some are more popular and in demand, and some are less so. This article discusses the main ways to learn English for students.

Modern methods of teaching English in higher education English is very popular in the modern world, moreover, it is the language of international communication and is known all over the world. There are many ways to teach English today. In addition, new ones are being developed on a regular basis so that now every teacher can choose the best performance methodology for himself.

At present, when teaching a foreign language in higher education institutions, classical methods are most often used.

AUDIOVISUAL AND AUDIO LINGUAL TECHNIQUES

The essence of both methods is to transmit the language through clear structures, memorization occurs through audio and video recordings. The audiovisual teaching method involves illustrating speech with appropriate pictures, that is, students are shown videos, feature films and documentaries in English. In this case, the trainees work simultaneously with two channels of perception visual and auditory, as a result of which associations arise in the students' heads, which makes it possible to better memorize the language. The purpose of the methods is to master a living, spoken language. Both methods are built on induction - training passes from the rule for example. Given all of the above, it can be noted that for university students who do not specialize in language learning, audio-lingual and audiovisual methods are suitable only if they are used in combination with other training programs.

COMMUNICATIVE METHOD

Currently, an increasing number of teachers are turning to a communicative method of learning English. The object of this method is speech itself, that is, such a technique first of all teaches to communicate. The communicative method involves a lot of student activity. The task of the teacher in this case will be to engage in the conversation all those present in the audience. For better memorization and use of the language, it is necessary to download all the channels of perception. The essence of the communicative method is to create real situations of communication. When reconstructing the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. A very important advantage of the communicative method can be considered that it has a huge variety of exercises: role-playing games, dialogs, simulation of real communication are used here.

At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammar-translation method. Most teachers of modern universities prefer these two methods, and often they are used in combination. The direct method is rarely used in higher education institutions, partly due to the lack of real native speakers among teachers, and partly because the level of students' preparation after school is too low. The audiovisual and audio-lingual methods in their pure form are not used at all, however, many university and institute teachers conduct classes from time to time based on such methods. This allows you to diversify the general educational program and interest students.[1]

1. Direct Method

This type of teaching involves giving students one-on-one instruction without any group work or activity involvement. This method is used in formal learning situations only and usually does not involve a lot of hands-on practice.

2. Indirect Method

In this style of teaching, students are first introduced to the material through group work or Activity- Based Learning activities before moving on to individual instruction. This method can be used in both formal and informal settings, and often results in better retention of information due to the student's increased understanding and engagement with the subject matter.

3. Interactive Methodology

This method is used when the teacher wants to engage their students in the learning process. The goal of this type of teaching is for students to have a hands-on experience with the material being taught. This method can be used in both formal and informal settings, and usually involves group work as well as individual instruction.

4. Step-by-Step Instruction

When using this methodology, teachers take an easy approach by breaking down complex topics in smaller pieces that students can understand easily. These steps are then guided step by step so that students reach the same goal simultaneously.

5. Group Work Model

This type of teaching method is widely used in K-12 settings, and it focuses on group work as a way to help students learn the material. In this style of learning, each student takes turns being

active learners, which allows them to share their own experiences and knowledge with the rest of the class.

6. Activity-Based Learning

This method involves breaking up large concepts into small pieces that can be easily remembered and applied in real-life situations. By using hands-on activities, ESL teachers hope to engage students in the learning process and help them retain the information learned.

7. Constructivist Methodology

This method is based on the idea that students learn best when they are actively involved in learning materials. In this type of teaching, students are given the freedom to explore new material on their own, which helps them better understand it

8. Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

This method focuses on developing fluency in a foreign language by using real-world, communicative activities. By engaging students in authentic conversations, CLT helps them to improve their comprehension and speaking skills.

9. Total Physical Response (TPR)

This type of teaching involves using physical activity in order to help students learn and remember information. By involving students in active learning activities that are both fun and physically challenging, TPR is said to be more effective than other methods when it comes to the retention of information.

10. An Eclectic Approach

This teaching method is a combination of several other methods and can be used to best meet the needs of individual students. There are a variety of teaching methods available to teachers, and it is important that they use the one that will be most effective for their specific situation and students.

The freedom to explore new material on their own, which helps them better understand it, is an important factor in choosing this type of teaching method.

11. The Grammar Translation Method

This method is based on the principle that language is composed of grammar and vocabulary, and that by understanding the structure of a foreign language, students can improve their comprehension. By using translation exercises as a way to introduce new grammar concepts, the Grammar Translation Method helps students to develop better fluency in their foreign languages.

12. The Structural Approach

This method focuses on the structure of a foreign language, specifically its grammar and vocabulary. By understanding how these elements work together, students are able to improve their comprehension skills.

13. The Silent Way

This method is based on the idea that language learning should be accompanied by minimalistic distractions. By focusing all class activities on the teaching of a specific grammar concept, students are able to focus and learn more effectively.

14. Suggestopedia

Suggestopedia is a method developed by Dr. Anthony Olshan that relies on the use of prompts to help students learn new information more effectively. These prompts can be used in conjunction with other teaching methods, or simply as an individual study guide. By using prompts, teachers are able to tailor learning opportunities specifically for their students and help them remember the material better.

15. Task-Based Language

This method is based on the premise that learning a language requires active engagement from students. By giving them hands-on tasks to complete, teachers are able to help students learn vocabulary and grammar in a fun and engaging way.[2]

New methods of teaching a foreign language are regularly developed, so now every teacher of the university can choose the most suitable method of work for himself. When teaching a foreign language in academic lyceums, task-based, project-based methods are most often used for communicative purposes.

The goal of these approaches and methods is to master a living, spoken language and to learn the ability to communicate. When using the communicative methods in teaching, students are more active. The task of the teacher in this case is the ability to involve everyone in the audience in the conversation. The essence of this method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. An important advantage of the method is that it has a variety of tasks: role-plays, discussions, debates, etc. According to Willis (1996), there are six types of tasks:

- Listing tasks: For example, students might have to make up a list of things they would pack if they were going on a beach vacation.
- Sorting and ordering: Students work in pairs and make up a list of the most important characteristics of an ideal vacation.
- Comparing: Students compare ads for two different supermarkets.
- Problem-solving: Students read a letter to an advice columnist and suggest a solution to the writer's problems. Sharing personal experience: Students discuss their reactions to an ethical or moral dilemma.
- Creative tasks: Students prepare plans for redecorating a house.[3]

So, the above mentioned methods are effective methods for teaching a foreign language. For example, work methods such as various quiz games, participation in international friendship clubs, organizing free conversations should be used more widely. Pupils and students should actively participate in these methods and show themselves. Because if he works on himself, he develops, searches, thinks independently and freely, and the range of thinking expands. By learning these new methods, we can make a small contribution to our country.

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